

Two-loop decentralized admittance control for a multi-manipulator system

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Abstract—The proposed decentralized strategy for cooperative object transportation consists of two steps. First, each robot estimates the wrenches applied to the object by all the other robots. Second, an admittance control scheme is used to limit internal wrenches. Experiments have been carried out with ABB Dual-arm YuMi and a UR5e robot, confirming the effectively reduction of internal wrenches.

Index Terms—Decentralized control, cooperative manipulation, multi-manipulator system

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative robot teams have been recently employed to reduce physical demands on human operators in tasks beyond the capabilities of a single agent, such as transporting large or heavy objects [1]. Moreover, decentralized and distributed strategies for cooperative control have been currently developed to improve scalability and robustness.

In multi-robot systems, particularly for transportation tasks, managing the wrenches exchanged with manipulators and the environment is a critical challenge. These wrenches must be controlled to minimize internal stresses that could compromise object integrity. Impedance and admittance control schemes [2], [3] are effective in regulating the interaction between the object and the environment.

II. OBJECT DYNAMICS

In the absence of interaction with the external environment, the object dynamics, can be written as

$$M_o(x_o)\ddot{x}_o + C_o(x_o, \dot{x}_o)\dot{x}_o + g_o = \begin{bmatrix} I_3 & O_3 \\ O_3 & T(\phi_o) \end{bmatrix}^T h_o,$$

where $x_o = [p_o^T \phi_o^T]^T$ (\dot{x}_o, \ddot{x}_o) is the object pose (generalized velocity, generalized acceleration), containing the object position and orientation, M_o is the inertia matrix, C_o is the matrix of the centripetal and Coriolis terms, g_o is the gravity term, h_o is the vector of wrenches exerted by the manipulators on the object and $T(\phi_o)$ is the matrix relating the derivative of the Euler angles, ϕ_o , to the object angular velocity, ω_o .

The wrench exerted on the object by the manipulators' end-effectors is

$$h_o = G h_e, \quad (1)$$

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where G is the *grasp matrix* [4] and h_e collects the wrenches exerted by each manipulator at its grasping points, i.e., $h_e = [h_1^T \ h_2^T \ \dots \ h_N^T]^T$. Since G has full row rank, an inverse solution of (1), proposed by [5], is

$$h_e = G^\dagger h_o + V h_i = h_E + h_I, \quad (2)$$

where G^\dagger is a right pseudo-inverse of G , $V \in \mathbb{R}^{6N \times (6N-6)}$ is a full column rank matrix spanning the null space of G , and $h_i \in \mathbb{R}^{6N-6}$ collects the independent wrenches that does not contribute to the object motion, usually referred as *internal wrenches*. The wrench balancing the object's dynamics, h_E , is given by

$$h_E = [h_{E_1}^T \ h_{E_2}^T \ \dots \ h_{E_N}^T]^T = G^\dagger G h_e, \quad (3)$$

while h_I , i.e., the collection of the robot contributes to the internal wrench, is

$$h_I = [h_{I_1}^T \ h_{I_2}^T \ \dots \ h_{I_N}^T]^T = V h_i = V V^\dagger h_e. \quad (4)$$

III. DECENTRALIZED WRENCH ESTIMATION

The internal wrench on the object remains unknown to the manipulators, since, in view of (4), it depends on the wrenches exerted by all the teammates. To overcome this drawback, in order to estimate all the wrenches exerted on the object, each manipulator runs a bank of $N - 1$ consensus-based estimators. Thus, the estimate of the wrench exerted by the k -th manipulator ($k = 1, \dots, N$) on the object computed by the i -th manipulator, ${}^i \hat{h}_k$, is obtained by

$${}^i \hat{h}_k(t) = k_0 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \left({}^j \hat{h}_k(t) - {}^i \hat{h}_k(t) \right), \quad (5)$$

where k_0 is a positive scalar gain. Based on the previous equation, each robot can estimate its own contribute to the internal wrenches defined in (4) as

$$\hat{h}_{I_i} = \Gamma_i V V^\dagger {}^i \hat{h}_e, \quad (6)$$

where $\Gamma_i = \{O_6 \ \dots \ \underbrace{I_6}_{i\text{-th robot}} \ \dots \ O_6\} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6N}$.

IV. DECENTRALIZED ADMITTANCE CONTROL

The local admittance controller receives as input the desired trajectory of the i -th end-effector and the estimate \hat{h}_{I_i} of the i -th robot contribute to the internal wrenches (6). The output is a reference trajectory, in terms of end-effector pose and generalized velocity and acceleration, computed as

Fig. 1. The communication graph among the 3 robots.

$$\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_{r_i} = \ddot{\mathbf{x}}_{d_i} + \mathbf{M}_i^{-1} \left[\mathbf{K}_{D_i} (\dot{\mathbf{x}}_{d_i} - \dot{\mathbf{x}}_{r_i}) + \mathbf{K}_{P_i} (\mathbf{x}_{d_i} - \mathbf{x}_{r_i}) + \mathbf{\Gamma}_i \mathbf{V} \mathbf{V}^\dagger {}^i \hat{\mathbf{h}}_e \right], \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{K}_{D_i} , \mathbf{K}_{P_i} and \mathbf{M}_i are (6×6) positive definite matrices of gains, representing, respectively, a virtual damping, stiffness and inertia imposed to the i -th end-effector motion.

Assumption 1: The connection between the i -th end-effector is modeled by introducing a grasp reference frame attached to the object linked to the i -th end-effector frame by a 6-DOFs spring system.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Consider a cooperative robotic cell composed of $N = 3$ arms (Fig. 1), a UR5e manipulator from Universal Robots and a dual-arm ABB YuMi robot, in charge of transporting a square-shaped wooden piece, whose size is $30 \times 30 \times 0.5$ cm, with $m_o = 0.250$ kg mass, in a decentralized manner.

At each time instant, the i -th robot receives the sensed wrench from its force-torque sensor, \mathbf{h}_i , and the wrenches estimation of its neighbours, ${}^i \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{j \neq i}$. Then, via (5), the i -th robot estimates the end-effector wrench collective vector ${}^i \hat{\mathbf{h}}_e$. Finally, by exploiting (7), each robot computes the reference trajectory in terms of position, velocity and acceleration.

The desired object barycenter trajectory consists of a translation along an arc of circumference with radius $r = 0.15$ m and angle $\theta_p = \pi/6$ rad, and a rotation along the z -axis of an angle $\theta_o = \pi/6$ rad.

A comparison with a pure positional controller has been carried out in order to test the effectiveness of the proposed estimator-controller architecture. Figure 2 compares the internal force and torque contributions of Robot 2 on the object, \mathbf{h}_{I_2} , in both the experiments. The internal wrenches reduction experienced with the proposed approach is remarkable, as well as the boundedness of the internal forces and torques. In the absence of the admittance control both $f_{I_{x,2}}$ and $\tau_{I_{z,2}}$ increase to dangerous levels. Conversely, this substantial decrease in internal wrenches does not result in any significant alteration in the trajectory commanded to the object, whose tracking errors are not affected by the presence of admittance controller, as depicted in Fig. 3. Errors are comparable with both approaches and can be mainly attributable to the wrench model adopted in Assumption 1. Finally, low-level control tracking errors are not reported since they are negligible.

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Fig. 2. Internal force contribution (on the left side) and torque contribution (on the right side) for Robot 2, in both the case studies: pure positional controller (on top), internal admittance controller (on bottom).

Fig. 3. Object tracking errors in the experiment with the pure positional controller (blue) and the admittance controller (orange).

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